

STATUS OF HEALTH PROGRAMS, ACTIVITIES AND CHALLENGES EXPERIENCED OF PERSONS DEPRIVED OF LIBERTY (PDLs) IN THE CORRECTIONAL FACILITIES IN METRO MANILA

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ABSTRACT

The health and well-being of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in the Philippines are the focus of this nursing research. PDLs encompass individuals in detention facilities awaiting trial, serving sentences, or under various custody forms, reflecting an international commitment to human rights within criminal justice systems. This study evaluates cell conditions, food quality, cleanliness, and overall well-being among PDLs while exploring international best practices to enhance their living conditions and mental health. Concerns such as elevated suicide rates and drug misuse underscore the critical mental health challenges faced by PDLs, exacerbated by prolonged incarceration. By providing insights into these issues, the research aims to inform prison administrators and policymakers on improving PDLs' well-being and treatment. The ultimate goal is to promote a humane and rights-based criminal justice system in the Philippines, thereby enhancing the health and quality of life for PDLs. Emphasizing the importance of comprehensive policies addressing health and well-being across structural and social dimensions, this study advocates for creating a supportive prison environment that prioritizes PDLs' health and facilitates their successful reintegration into society.

Keywords: *Persons Deprived of Liberty, prison conditions, mental health, Philippines, criminal justice reform*

INTRODUCTION

The health of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in the Philippines is an urgent matter that has to be addressed. The overall health issues that inmates in the nation deal with

have been the subject of several studies. Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) environment should be a top-tier priority due to the overwhelming crowd inside the prison. Unsafe cells have far-reaching consequences. Prison (un)safety is instrumentally alarming because it implies future increases in criminal reoffending and public health problems. Higher reoffending rates are associated with lower prisoner health and poorer prison living quality (Auty & Liebling, 2020). Furthermore, prison health is public health. Considering the conditions under which they are being held, the persons deprived of liberty (PDLs) are still human and deserves humane treatment. Authorities have deteriorated already inadequate health, preventing access to healthcare and productive activities (Ismail, 2019). PDLs health is deteriorating, which is critical for behavior change and has serious consequences for re-entry results.

Rehabilitation starts at their health changes and strategies how the coping mechanism they have in their environment. Prison systems often neglect physical activities, resulting in unhealthy living conditions due to overcrowding and limited opportunities. Despite this, many inmates who do engage in sports, dancing, and games report significant physical and mental benefits. Research indicates that the psychological and relaxing effects of these activities are positively correlated with participation in games and sports (Baldonado et al., 2022). The prison environment significantly impacts inmates' physical and mental health. Challenges include safety concerns for transgender inmates (Brown, 2014), stigma and anxiety for sexual offenders (Blagden et al., 2014), and overall stress and anxiety due to the restrictive and unease-inducing nature of prison life. The environment also hampers effective communication and access to healthcare, particularly for those with disabilities or special needs (Perrett et al., 2019; Dodd et al., 2022). These conditions hinder social skills and reintegration into society post-release (Januin et al., 2023).

Emotional well-being is crucial for inmates, especially older individuals with mental health conditions (Lima et al., 2022). Studies highlight the importance of addressing the emotional challenges faced by aging prisoners and the need for supportive relationships to enhance self-efficacy and overall well-being (Lorito et al., 2017; Crewe et al., 2013; Noujaim et al., 2017). A comprehensive approach to emotional support within the prison system is necessary. Access to healthcare in prisons is limited by various barriers, including judicial obstacles and the impacts of the war on drugs (Shortis et al., 2022; Beckett et al., 2005). Ensuring community-equivalent healthcare and addressing transitional care between prison and the community are crucial for the well-being and rehabilitation of inmates (Simpson et al., 2021; Abbott et al., 2017).

The availability and accessibility of healthcare facilities within prisons are critical. Spatial accessibility to medical services, including maternity services for women, plays a significant role in ensuring adequate healthcare (Tao et al., 2020; Paynter et al., 2020). Evaluating and improving the distribution of these facilities can help address healthcare disparities (Jin et al., 2019). Providing necessary medical services, especially for managing infectious diseases like HIV/AIDS, is essential (Pedroso et al., 2023). Addressing the physical activities, environmental conditions, emotional wellness, healthcare access, and facility availability in prisons is vital for improving the health and well-being of inmates. This requires a comprehensive and empathetic approach that recognizes the unique needs of different inmate populations.

This study also aims to learn more about the conditions within the cells, the cleanliness of the surroundings, and the well-being of the PDLs. The study also hopes to discover different approaches used by other nations in dealing with situations of this nature, and it hopes to implement any ideas or strategies learned there to aid the Philippines' environment and PDLs. According to a report by the National Library of Medicine, "suicide rates among prisoners are six times higher than those of the general population, raising concerns about their mental health." This is more common for PDLs who have been in jail for more than a year; they claim that they misused drugs for their self-control or to relax; many of them have poor mental health which causes anger, frustration, and anxiety. They also claimed that they misused drugs for their self-control.

Understanding the larger environmental and organizational variables that lead to poor mental health in prisons should be given more thought. Additionally, this data can be utilized to guide administrators and decision-makers in the jail system.

Research Questions

The study generally aims to evaluate and determine the public health challenges faced by the Filipino Persons Deprived of Liberty or PDLs of Metro Manila. Specifically, this research aims to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the current state of PDLs in Correctional Facilities in Metro Manila, and its impact to their overall well-being?
2. What healthcare activities are implemented in the Correctional Facilities in Metro Manila?
3. What are the primary obstacles encountered by Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in the Correctional Facilities of Metro Manila?
4. What are the recommended comprehensive measures and strategies to effectively address the various health concerns of persons deprived of liberty (PDLs) in Metro Manila's correctional system, while promoting a holistic and rehabilitative approach?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers utilized a descriptive qualitative research approach to assess an overview of the current health programs, activities, and obstacles in Metro Manila facilities. Semi-structured interviews were utilized to gather data with the aim to gather valuable insights directly from healthcare professionals, enhancing the understanding of the health-related conditions within the correctional facility. The study followed with a phenomenological design involving coding key concepts, organizing codes into themes, and refining them for meaningful insights, particularly in exploring human experiences and perspectives.

The research locale was conducted within Metro Manila (Parañaque City), Philippines. The study targets Healthcare workers and nurses who have a minimum of one year of experience working with PDLs in correctional facilities, have a comprehensive understanding of the health programs in place, and can provide insights into the well-being of PDLs and officers who have a minimum of one year experience and roles in the day-to-day functioning of the correctional facilities. Their perspectives are essential for understanding the overall conditions within the facilities. Lastly, supervisors and chief wardens hold leadership positions within the facilities. Purposive sampling was used to determine data saturation, guaranteeing a comprehensive representation of diverse perspectives. Data sources, such as healthcare providers and administrators, bolster the study's credibility. The participants are provided with the findings to validate and ensure that their viewpoints are faithfully portrayed.

Furthermore, the research used a Roy's Adaptation Model (1976) framework to interpret the data acquired. Data consists of things that may be assessed based on respondents' perceptions. Before the questionnaire was ready for the interview, the researchers underwent an evaluative assessment, which assured the guided questionnaire's validity with three (3) validators who checked for content adequacy, lack of bias, and relevance. Feedback on potential modifications was encouraged. The documents and authorization letter required for data gathering have been managed.

Before data collection, the researchers sought assistance from the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology in the National Capital Region, Philippines, to reach potential participants. With the assistance of officers and wardens, the researchers found participants needed for data collection. The data-gathering procedure was conducted from April 3rd and April 26th, 2024. For ethical considerations, Informed Consent was given before proceeding with the interview. Finally, the researchers coded key concepts, organized codes into themes, and analyzed the participants' responses.

RESULTS

Comprehensive Wellness rehabilitation program for PDL's

This theme describes the Person Deprived of Liberty (PDL) and the need for proper access to services that can help their health and well-being. The facilities offer activities and programs that address the physical, mental, emotional, and sometimes spiritual needs of the PDLs. Regular exercise and indoor and outdoor sports aim to encourage physical health and teamwork. The monthly Frolics program is arranged to promote social interaction, enjoyment, and closeness through these events. Mental health needs are catered to through therapeutic interventions and counseling sessions, offering support to address psychological needs and personal challenges. The implementation of the livelihood program gives the PDLs opportunities to develop skills and improve their personal lives. These programs provide vocational training and job readiness courses based on the needs of the person by providing PDLs with practical skills. To improve their possibility of finding work and reintegrating into society after they are released. It also

helps build a purpose and self-worth, motivating them to make positive changes in their life.

1. Comprehensive Wellness Rehabilitation Program at the Correctional Facilities in Metro Manila

Table 1. Comprehensive Wellness rehabilitation program for PDL's

Themes	Subthemes
Comprehensive Wellness and Rehabilitation	Regular Exercise Regimen
	Monthly Frolics Program
	Scheduled Sport Activities
	Therapeutic Intervention and Community Programs
	Comprehensive Health Strategy
	Counseling and Psychological Interventions
	Variety of Recreational Options
	Comfortable Accommodations
	Routine and Structure
Cultivating Health and Building Resilience	Improved physical health
	Improved mental health
	Positive outlook in life
Holistic Wellness and Engagement Activities	Regular morning exercise and sunning
	Implementation of Livelihood programs
	Sport activities
	Board games for entertainment

As stated by the participant “ *Mas hinahanap na nila yung activities kasi nabu-bored sila sa loob ng jail, sa loob ng cell. So, yung mga activities, pag-gising pa lang sa umaga, nagkakaroon na sila ng activities. Exercises, minsan umiikot sila sa loob ng cell, minsan sa buong floor. Tapos, naglilinis, may kanya-kanya silang mga responsibilities. Tapos, after nun, pagkatapos ng mga prayer, yan. So, ano yun, sa psychology, nakakatulong sa kanila yun...Pag dating naman ng gabi, yan pa rin. Madalas, ah, pelikula na naka save, mga movies. Yun. So, yun matakaw sila dyan sa panunood.*” The participant said that PDLs are more likely to look for distractions and activities so they do not get bored throughout the day. Sports are the foundation of a healthy life, and physical activity is necessary for physical and mental health (Warburton & Bredin, 2017) (White et al., 2017).

As stated by Jail Officer “*Meron din naman tayong ginagawa na program every month yan. May naman tayong naka-structured na mga program. And yung mas-awaited na program, yung National Correctional Consciousness Week, it's a one-week na activity yun ng BJMP na parang that is correctional week. Parang foundation day natin.... Every month kasi may mga ano eh, ang tawag dito, meron tayong mga occasions. So as much as possible, meron tayong program per month.*” According to the officer, the more they are engaged in program activities, the less they can think of bad things like running away. Participation in monthly programs and activities encourages social interaction and a sense of building closeness and brotherhood inside (Elena & Nansy, 2022). Regular socializing lessens the feeling of loneliness and isolation and leads to better mental health for the PDLs.

Implemented Health Care Activities in the Correctional Facilities

The following theme describes the Person's Deprived of Liberty (PDL) involvement in holistic and wellness activities. These activities involve implementing various procedures and programs in correctional facilities that address the PDL's overall health. These programs aim to meet patients' mental, emotional, and occasionally spiritual requirements in addition to their physical wellness. Correctional facilities strive to create an environment that supports rehabilitation and personal development by providing access to programs and services that include physical exercise regimens, mental health counseling, educational opportunities, artistic expression outlets, social connection initiatives, and accommodations for diverse spiritual or religious practices. These all-encompassing strategies aim to lower recidivism rates by enabling people to overcome obstacles, create healthy coping strategies, and learn skills that enable a smooth transition back into society.

Balancing Privacy and Practicality explores how to navigate privacy laws to ensure respectful communication and resource access. Breaking Barriers in Facing Stigma and Health Disparities seeks to combat discrimination against (PDLs) and marginalized genders, fostering equality in healthcare. Transparency in restroom design is also promoted. Physical fitness programs and activities encourage paid labor and inclusive sports participation. They also support frequent outdoor activities like sunbathing to improve general health.

2. Health Care Activities

Table 2. Implemented Health Care Activities in the Correctional Facilities

Themes	Subthemes
Breaking Barriers in Facing Stigma and Health Disparities	Stigma among PDLs
	Attitude toward marginalized gender
Balancing Privacy and Practicality	Privacy laws
	Consent and communication
	Transparent restroom
Physical fitness activities / program	Sports programs
	Compensated labor
	Regular sunning

Jail Officer in Male Dorm mention about the stigma among PDLs is about HIV and the participant said is “Well basically, *yung rule of law natin na bawal silang ipagkalat, yung confidentiality natin number one yun. And then...With regular, kasi maintenance na kasi inom nila eh. So continuous, yes continuous yung medications nila. In the follow up check up kasama nila.*” Healthcare providers play a crucial role in the lives of PLHIV, but stigma and discrimination among medical care providers towards HIV patients can hinder effective prevention and treatment efforts (Elamin et al., 2019). Discrimination by healthcare providers, such as administering HIV tests without consent, refusing treatment, or disclosing confidential information, can lead to negative consequences (Dong et al., 2018). Additionally, discrimination due to adolescent HIV can indirectly impact retention in care through increased internalized stigma (Pantelic et al., 2020).

As stated by Jail Officer 2 shares about the attitude toward marginalized gender that “*Uhh, ideally dapat talaga naka-naka-separate ng pdl with special needs Bakit sila nagsama dun sa special needs? Kasi syempre meron silang special attention na pwedeng dapat na pinoprovide natin sa kanila so ang mga senior citizen nakahiwalay yan, ang mga kinaklasify kasi natin dito sa jail pagdating na na dito, kinaklasify natin sila. Ito para sa mga petty crimes lang, o mababa lang mga kaso nito. Ito para sa mga gantong age range. Ito para sa mga matataas ang mga kaso nito sa dorm nito. Dito ang mga senior citizens, and PWD para sa sama sila. Sigurong, kinaklasify din natin. Pero with regards to the transgender, hindi natin sinaseperate, nahiwalay. Sinasama natin sila, doon pa rin sa mga cells. Pero if open naman ang jail management,*

kung may mga violation against them, halimbawa, may harassment na ginagawa sa kanila”.

It is essential to consider the influence of education and prior experiences on attitudes towards marginalized groups, as training programs and exposure to diverse perspectives can help foster more inclusive attitudes (Nayak, 1999; Özkan & Küçükkelepçe, 2019). Additionally, societal attitudes toward gender roles and norms can affect perceptions of marginalized genders, highlighting the importance of promoting egalitarian views (Beji & Murat, 2022; Trogrlić et al., 2020). Factors such as age, gender, and personal experiences have been identified as significant influences on attitudes toward various social issues, including substance use disorders (Abuhammad et al., 2022).

As stated by the Jail officer in the male dormitory, *“Monthly may tinatawag kami ang Frolics. Frolics yung parang... Parang.. Masayang program. Para malibang sila. Then afternoon may schedule kami dito sa taas, sila naglalaro sila ng volleyball, badminton, basketball, and yung mga activities sila dito.”* Implementing sports programs in correctional facilities has been shown to impact the physical and mental well-being of incarcerated individuals positively. Research indicates that sports can improve prisoners' general health, emotional management, and self-perception (Arana et al., 2018). Furthermore, sports-based interventions have been found to motivate imprisoned individuals in reentry programs, ultimately aiming to reduce reoffending rates (Meek & Lewis, 2013). These programs promote physical activity and promote health initiatives within prison settings (Meek & Lewis, 2012).

As stated by Jail Officer in Male Dormitory *“From the deped, meron tayong ALS. And ano tesda, pumapasok dito. So they already have the skills bago lumabas.”* In the Philippines, providing education to individuals deprived of liberty, such as those in prison, is crucial for rehabilitation and reintegration into society. The Department of Education (DepEd), Commission on Higher Education (CHED), and Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) have been recommended to expand their community services to enhance the delivery of the Alternative Learning System (ALS) among incarcerated individuals (Petrola et al., 2022). ALS is a non-formal education program that can help prisoners acquire essential skills and knowledge.

As stated by Chief Jail Nurse Male mentions that *“Yung privacy kasi parang mawawala sa'yo kung ikaw ay nakulong. Paano ba yan? Parang pila-pila ang pag punta sa CR minsan, sabay-sabay pa. I mean, LIGO. Hindi naman yung pupunta sa CR mismo, as in comfort room, sa ligoan. Minsan may oras yung pagligo, minsan sabay-sabay”.* In providing a transparent restroom for a person deprived of liberty, it is essential to consider the ethical implications and human rights aspects associated with such facilities. Persons deprived of liberty, whether in prisons, healthcare facilities, or other settings, often face challenges in accessing essential services, including healthcare (Pedroso et al., 2023).

As stated by Jail officer 2 Male Dormitory mentions that *“On a regular basis there are sunning as well as sports fest for physical activities”.* In the context of persons deprived of liberty in the Philippines, engaging in physical activities can be a beneficial and constructive approach. Research has shown that individuals deprived of their liberty often

face challenges related to health, access to proper nutrition, and limited physical exercise opportunities (Hattori et al., 2020). Encouraging physical activity among this population can help address these issues and promote overall well-being. A study conducted in a district jail in the Philippines aimed to determine the types of physical activities available to persons deprived of liberty and their level of satisfaction with these activities (Baldonado et al., 2022). Implementing structured physical activity programs within correctional facilities can improve physical health and contribute to mental well-being and social interaction among inmates.

Chief Jail Nurse Female dormitory mentions that *“May consent siyempre. May consent. Di namin sila pinipinit. Kasi isang ano yun eh, diba bawal.”* In the Philippines, obtaining consent for HIV screening among persons deprived of liberty is crucial to uphold their rights and dignity. International human rights laws emphasize the importance of obtaining consent before subjecting individuals to HIV testing. This requirement aligns with the need to respect the liberty and security of individuals, especially those in vulnerable situations such as incarceration (Eba, 2015). Providing healthcare services, including HIV testing and treatment, to persons deprived of liberty is essential for their well-being and is mandated by laws in various countries (Pedroso et al., 2023; Cardoso et al., 2022; Bossonario et al., 2020).

Primary Obstacles encountered by PDLs at the Correctional Facilities in Metro Manila

Within correctional institutions, PDL presents particular healthcare difficulties that need careful attention to protocol enforcement, schedule adherence, and the creation of rules to maintain orderliness. Even with these initiatives, there are still obstacles to receiving healthcare, such as a shortage of specialized clinics, inadequate medical equipment, and budgetary limitations. Court rulings requiring proper medical treatment emphasize how urgent it is to solve these issues. In addition, pregnant people in correctional settings must get compassionate treatment according to the principles of maternal health equity.

According to certain participants, health aid is available inside the cell for them 24 hours a day, and they also mentioned whether or not there was a sick person inside the cell. They added that the PDLs consistently adhered to the facilities' timetable and procedures and always respected the area's cleanliness and regulation. Some participants also mentioned that they did not have enough medicine for PDLs who depended on it for daily requirements. Indeed, the area needs more money to meet PDLs' needs in some areas. Regarding the prenatal checkup, they stated that it is scheduled and that hospital support is always available nearby.

3. Primary Obstacles

Table 3. Primary Obstacles encountered by PDLs at the Correctional Facilities in Metro Manila

Themes	Subthemes
Protocol enforcement	Schedule and routine
	Policy for orderliness
Addressing Healthcare Barriers and Improving Access in Correctional Facilities	Lack of medical equipment
	Lack of clinic
	Court order for adequate medical care
	Financial constraints
Ensuring and Compassionate Care in Maternal Health Equity	Prenatal Checkup
	Lactation area
	Hospital assistance
	Prenatal care is provided in a female dorm

As stated by the participants *“mula 5 o’clock ano na yan start na ng gising nila. Ano na yan start na kami ng zumba. May mga uh personal na ano na rin sila uh breakfast. Uh rest and relaxation, meron na rin silang uh when it comes to relaxation wala talagang uh activity. Ako prefer ko kasi kaya sinasabi ko rin sa kanila na kahit yung sunday meron man lang tayong day in a week na medyo pahinga kayo, lie low kayo sa mga activities para makapahinga rin naman”* The participants said that PDLs are entirely engaged inside the facilities. The cultural program seeks to foster a sense of camaraderie among PDLs, growth of self-confidence, and the sharing of cultural abilities as a constructive kind of entertainment. Dance, music, theater/drama, and art workshops are among the cultural activities permitted for prisoners (BJMP 2024).

Other participants said *“ Sa medical supplies. Huwag medicines ma'am ah. Halimbawa, suwero, halimbawa butterfly. Ano lahat to? Ilalapit ko lahat kay Warden. Sir, wala na po tayong ganto.”* The facilities can provide basic needs for medication or necessary things medical supplies inside the area, but when it comes to more specific medical needs they

need to notify the warden first, one of the participants said that Lahat naman ng medical needs ng PDL na aattend, kung may kailangan for laboratory, bukas kung yung medical mission kung ano yung nirequest ng doctor, tina triage din namin yun. Kung sino yung sense of urgency, kung urgent pa ba, selective, yun ang ginagawa namin. Kung masakit naman sila, nadadala naman namin sila sa hospital kasi malapit lang yung hospital dito, nadaanan ninyo na yun.” It is stated that they can offer medical support to PDLs who require laboratory testing and urgent hospital needs at a doctor's request. If they cannot arrive, they will be admitted to the hospital because the current hospital is quite far away. According to the (BJMP 2024), they offer medical services. PDL health services include illness promotion, prevention, treatment, and rehabilitation interventions. When a PDL is accepted, they have a medical evaluation. During their incarceration, PDLs get regular health monitoring, medical consultations, health education and counseling, and medication, if available. PDLs can exercise and receive daily sun exposure to maintain their physical health.

As stated by the participants *“Prenatal niya. Naka-schedule naman yun. So ano naman yun, Madali na kausap ang court. Naka-schedule na siya. Lahat na ng ating services na available doon sa hospital, dadalhin nalang natin si Buntis.”* while the other participants said *“Pagdating sa maternal, prenatal, dinadala namin muna sa barangay. sa barangay muna and then i-endorse ng barangay dyan sa OSPA. Wala kaming namimiss na prenatal minsan pa mas nasasamahan ko yung PDL sa kanyang prenatal kesa dun sa asawa ng sa nag-prenatal.”* Regarding prenatal care, one of them noted that BJMP never skips a prenatal checkup for PDLs. *“minsan mas nasasamahan ko yung PDL sa kanyang prenatal kesa dun sa asawa ko”* This indicates that they provided excellent care for PDLs in need of prenatal support. According to one study, the jail should designate a space easily accessible for all required prenatal and postnatal care and treatments. This space can also be used as a nursery suitable for nursing newborns delivered to a mother-PDL, provided that trained staff is present and the facility is always used with the child's best interests in mind (Borlongan, 2021).

Improvement and Referrals

This describes the Person's Deprived of Liberty (PDL) access to health services through facilities and other forms. This involves using correctional facilities' healthcare infrastructure corresponding with treatment standards; certain participants state that they have scheduled routine medication distribution and continuous nursing supervision in every cell with nursing aids available inside to give them the report. Some participants also brought up comprehensive prenatal care and hospital support for their pregnant PDLs. This term encapsulates the idea that pregnant individuals receive thorough and consistent prenatal check-ups, ensuring they receive appropriate medical attention and support leading up to delivery. Additionally, it highlights the importance of hospital assistance in providing necessary care and support during labor, delivery, and the postpartum period, further emphasizing the comprehensive nature of the services provided to pregnant individuals.

4. Recommendation

Table 4.1. Improvement and Referrals

Themes	Subthemes
Modernized and Well-Maintained Facilities	Utilization of appliances for ventilation
	Removal of excess non-essential belongings
	Supply of potable water
Prompt hospital referral for pregnant PDLs	Regular check ups
	Hospital assistance

The infrastructure and environment in which care is delivered from the first line of defense: Their modernized, maintained healthcare units are critical to ensuring that the sick behind bars receive the required attention. They are responsible for on-the-spot general health care needs and addressing emergency medical situations within prisons. Facilities were invested in modernization, using appliances for ventilation and removing excess unessential objects to make the environment or providing potable water alongside an effortful landscaping plan that follows suit with sustainable agriculture principles; they create not only a place where healing and good health can thrive but also someplace where healthy living becomes possible. Through this upgrading work, not only does the quality of care get better, but it also maintains the dignity and rights of the people living there.

Chief Jail Nurse in Female Dorm mentions that “*may mga provided naman ang electric fan dyan. As of now ngayon talaga mainit.*” added by the Jail Officer shares that “*Okay lang, sa ventilation talaga passing through lang yung ano tawag dito, yung air jan. So syempre, iiwasan din natin. Since yun na nga lang yung way of entry and exit ng air within the facility. Kasi kung... So ngayon, especially ngayon, na sobrang init. Talagang... Kailangan yun. Marami lang talaga tayong window. Syaka may canopy. Pero grilled yun. Highly secured naman yun. Naka-double grills yun. Pero yun lang. Iniiwasan lang natin na walang mga blockage doon. Kasi yung iba, nagalagay sila ng... Kung alam niyo yung term na kubol na tinatawag. o parang naggagawa sila ng parang nilalagyan na ng kurtina yung mga cells o yung mga higaan nila yung mga bunks so yun, ina-avoid natin yun tinatangal natin yun para at least minimize yung ay hindi, ma-ano talaga natin ma-maximize yung flow ng air in yung ventilation Kasi talaga wala talaga tayong magagawa. Nasa Pilipinas tayo alam natin nyan, mainit talaga dito. And syempre hindi rin natin sila pwedeng ganda ng air conditioning system. Number one, that is very... costly yun, very expensive yun on the part of the government. Kasi pinapakain na nga natin sila, alamin na ba kung gaano kalaki ang ginagasos. Actually liability ng government ang mga PDL. Kasi siyempre, pinapakain natin sila. At the same time kung mag-air ka pa sila, dagdag*

pa yun sa cost. So okay na lang nung may mga fan. Inaano natin naman, mayroon tayong mga exhaust fan diyan. Mayroon din tayong mga... mayroon din sila mga fan per dorm. Na talaga enough naman para well ventilated yung air.”

As both participants mentioned, the care provided by correctional officers and healthcare professionals plays a significant role in safeguarding inmates' physical and mental health. Several studies have highlighted the importance of adequate healthcare services and the role of officers in ensuring the safety and well-being of individuals in custody. In addition to improving the health of PDLs, attending to these requirements as soon as possible has been shown by studies to lower criminality and, eventually, imprisonment rates. Moreover, Programs that offer support in these areas have been shown to enhance rehabilitation efforts. Furthermore, organizational factors and community involvement are crucial in prisoner rehabilitation and reintegration (Santora & Lillefjell, 2014).

Warden in Female dorm mentions that “*so before ako mag one month nawala na yung mga kurtina kaya nakikita nyo po sila through and through. Nagpatanggal ako ng mga excess as in sobrang dami ng uh di lang gamit, daga. Which is natakot ako. Sabi ko bakit napakaraming daga. As in parang may- may naghahabulan sila in you front talaga. Ang lalaki talaga as in di sila natatakot. Only to find out na napakarami naming gamit sa loob. Napakarami nang excess. Meron ako pinalabas sa kanila na ‘ito lang po yung kailangan na nasa jail’. Uh sa ngayon, nasa process pa rin ako kaya ayan mero nyung staff namin. Meron sila na dorm by dorm sila tapos nag account sila ‘ano yung gamit mo?’ so ito hindi pwede, tanggal. Tapos another one is pag nagge-greyhound kami, everyday may greyhound eh, almost everyday. So pag may nakikita na ‘ito hindi dapat to dahil according sa napagusapan’ so tatanggalin natin either ipauwi mo sa family mo or.”*

The participants need to be more concerned about considering the impact of overcrowding and clutter on indoor air quality and overall living conditions. Research has shown that overcrowded and cluttered living spaces can lead to poor ventilation, which in turn can contribute to the spread of airborne diseases and increase the risk of respiratory infections among PDLs. Inadequate ventilation in overcrowded residences has been linked to an increased risk of tuberculosis transmission (Ramaliba et al., 2017). To address the issue of poor ventilation in overcrowded and cluttered living spaces, it is essential to implement strategies to improve airflow and air quality. This may include regular cleaning to reduce dust and allergens, decluttering for better air circulation, and ensuring ventilation systems function correctly. In conclusion, overcrowded and cluttered living spaces can lead to poor ventilation, which can have negative implications for the health and well-being of inhabitants. By prioritizing proper ventilation and reducing overcrowding and clutter, it is possible to create healthier indoor environments and mitigate the risks of poor air quality.

A Warden in the Female dorm shared that “*nagrequest din ako sa uh Maynilad, sana ma-approve. Uh nagrequest ako ng fountain. Kasi ano eh ano nga yung tawag dito. Uhm syempre yung tubig dito syempre di naman lahat potable. Uhm ang PDL kung san naman talaga- even tayo matipid diba. Hindi naman lahat yan may kakayanang bumili ng mineral*

water. So kahit saan lang yan iinom. Sa gripo. Eh hindi naman natin sure kung potable yung diba yung nasa gripo. So what we did, isa sa request namin kay Maynilad is baka meron silang mabigay na yung fountain. Kasi uh meron silang uh inapprove sa ano sa ibang- may nalaman kaming inaprubahan nila sa ibang jail”.

The participant requested potable water with the assurance of clean, drinkable water to ensure hydration and promote the health of the PDLs. Prisons struggle with inadequate sanitary facilities, dangerous and polluted water supplies, and water scarcity. The lack of access to clean water, overcrowding, and inadequate sanitation facilities have exacerbated the spread of diseases within prison environments (Hout, 2022; Mhlanga-Gunda et al., 2022). The right to clean water is crucial for maintaining the health and well-being of PDLs, and the failure to provide this basic necessity can lead to protests and riots among incarcerated individuals (Mhlanga-Gunda et al., 2022).

Pregnant PDLs receive thorough prenatal care, frequent checkups, and quick access to required medical procedures by placing a high priority on rapid referrals. This supports pregnant people's access to appropriate healthcare, regardless of their circumstances, and also encourages favorable outcomes for both the mother and the fetus.

A Jail Officer shared that “Well, basically number one would be regular check-up. Regular check-up. Because monitoring the baby is very important. Noh? Including... vaccines hindi lang para sa vitamins really good vitamins” Added by the Chief Health Service that “Ito pag may buntis kami... Kapag may dala dito sa aming buntis... I prenatal namin sila agad. I-request namin sa court na need ng prenatal checkups, Tapos, ayun. Pag nanganak, yan, tatakbo din namin yun sa hospital. Tapos, yung check-ups nila, ano talaga, kung ano yung date na ano. Talagang follow-up talaga. Meron naman sila.”

Regular check-ups and medical assistance provided by correctional facilities play a crucial role in addressing the healthcare needs of incarcerated individuals. Regular check-ups and hospital assistance for pregnant inmates are crucial to ensure the well-being of both the mother and the developing fetus. Research emphasizes the importance of better policies, enforcement, and standard practices to improve the health and welfare of pregnant incarcerated women (Kelsey et al., 2017). Early and regular prenatal care is highlighted as essential in preventing adverse outcomes for pregnant women (Ssetaala et al., 2020). Additionally, stresses the significance of providing dietary supplements, nutritious meals, and nutritional counseling to incarcerated pregnant women, although adherence to these guidelines in jail facilities may be lacking (Forestell & Dallaire, 2018). Incarceration presents unique challenges in providing healthcare services due to factors such as limited budgets, high inmate turnover, and larger inmate volumes. Despite these challenges, it is essential to streamline care for pregnant inmates to ensure they receive necessary check-ups and assistance during their pregnancy (Yi et al., 2016). Additionally, nursing care plays a significant role in supporting pregnant women during their incarceration and the postpartum period (“Nursing Care of Incarcerated Women During Pregnancy and the Postpartum Period,” 2018).

Behavioral Management and Protocol among the PDL Population

Correctional institutions come with conducting behavioral management implemented in the facility among the PDLs that comes with the rules and protocols. This theme describes the protocol management inside the facility with the officers' initiative and the PDLs' cooperation and how they abide by the rules. Creating programs for inmate development to get them ready for their ultimate reintegration into society is the primary goal of the Directorate for Inmates Welfare and Development. The Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) implements the Therapeutic Community Modality Program (TCMP), which intends to change people's thinking and behavior through structured processes. The TCMP has four interconnected developmental aspects: behavior management, emotional and psychological, intellectual and psychological, and vocational and survival skills.

Table 4.2. Behavioral Management and Protocol among the PDL Population

Themes	Subthemes
Holistic Wellness and Engagement Activities	Regular morning exercise and sunning
	Implementation of Livelihood Programs
	Sport Activities
	Board games for entertainment
Protocol Enforcement	Schedule and routine
	Policy for orderliness
Comprehensive Wellness and Rehabilitation	Regular Exercise Regimen
	Monthly Frolics Program
	Scheduled Sport Activities
	Therapeutic Intervention and Community Programs
	Comprehensive Health Strategy
	Counseling and Psychological Interventions

	Variety of Recreational Options
	Comfortable Accommodations
	Routine and Structure

As stated by one of the participants, *“Oo, meron. Kasi part yun ng TCMP program noh. Pagkagising nila hanggang sa pagtulog nila yun yung TCMP program. So meron silang final accounting dito by 10.30 p.m. So that after that final accounting na 10.30, dapat ano na yun, tulog na silang lahat. Kasi gigising sila the next morning at 5 am. Kasi start na sila ng exercise tapos mag-almusal na sila.”*. The participant stated that the PDLs act according to the routines they follow in their daily activities. The routine comprises waking up and sleeping at the scheduled time, doing recreational activities throughout the day, and relaxing in their free time. These activities promote self-growth and self-discipline to improve their well-being in the correctional facility. An increase in the length of physical activities in jail has been recognized as one of the several approaches that will have the most beneficial impact in decreasing inmates' high risks of many diseases and improving prisoners' health and well-being (Mukiza, 2014).

Another participant shared, *“Yung program na yan ay yung therapeutic community modality program or yung TCMP diyan naman kasi ang focus niyan is to address nga yung behavior ng mga PDL natin. So kung halimbawa ay talagang problem sila sa community, kung doon nagkakaroon sila ng parang conflict with the community, conflict with the family, we are trying na i-reassess nila, i-reevaluate nila yung sarili nila through that program para mas mad-discover din nila yung sarili nila. Kasi para siyang ano eh, para siyang... counseling, group counseling isa yun sa ginagawa natin para program dito hindi lang sa focus sa medical condition siyempre holistic kasi tayo dapat diba hindi lang focus tayo sa isang bagay hindi tinitignan din natin yung pwedeng natin maitulong sa kanya holistically kasama dun yung behavior nila psychological, ganyan may mga psychological ano din tayo dito may counseling na ginagawa, may naman psychological interventions especially kung meron sila may psychiatric patients din ano sila so actually iba-iba na pwede ko pang i-discuss na yan pero mostly yun lang naman pa sa ngayon, actually exercise zumba nag - ganyan sila, nag coconduct sila dito ng stress ano tawag dito, stress management every day may stress management sila kasi syempre we know now you are a person deprived of liberty talaga syempre since you are parang separated from your family yung liberty mo talaga wala din, at talagang pinagkait sayo most of our clients stressed sila talagang in the first months or years nalang nalang nandito in denial pa yan, parang ayaw pa nila na... Bat yun, since yun tinatulongan din natin sila holistically, not only medically pero ah mas i-address natin yung consensual condition din.”*. The participant shared their approach to how they help the PDLs not just in their health but also in terms of their psychological and emotional well-being. According to BJMP (2024), the program teaches and models positive thinking, pro-social values, sound decision-making, and positive coping. The program teaches the participants how to cope in an environment away from the norm with positive thinking and approach to their life in the

facility through a psychological approach and recreational activities. They deal with the PDLs through counseling and stress management to address their needs.

Another participant stated *“Meron tayong tinatawag na TCMP. Hindi sya- hindi ko sya maconsidered na recreational. Uh pero sya yung parang backbone ng aming buong programs. TCMP stands for Therapeutic Community Modality Program. Lahat ng jails nagaano yan, kaya ala singko pa lang gising na sila kasi nakalagay na yan sa aming schedule. Hanggang pagtulog nila, lahat ng ginawa nila nakabond yan doon sa TCMP namin. So may mga nakalagay don about TV viewing, may oras kami ng panonood, siguro part ng recreational. Meron din sila, hindi lang umaga na zumba. Uh nag-ano kasi kami ng mga over- lalo na yung mga overweight, yung mga ano natin. Uh may additional silang extra uh exercise sa hapon.”*. The different recreational activities that are implemented for the PDLs includes morning sunning, zumba, and additional exercise for the overweight PDLs.

Another participant stated the protocol when it comes to orderliness among the PDLs, *“Actually sila-sila mismo sa baba eh kasi pagpasok nila diyan may rule na bawal mag ingay. So kapag kagaling sa personnel, lalo pag galing sa personnel, automatic yan.”* The noise pollution in the facility is neutralized by having the rule that they are not allowed to produce any noise that is concerning. The PDLs are disciplined when it comes to orderliness in their dorms.

According to Mukiza (2014), he stated that first, there was a statistically significant decrease in the rate of depression, low levels of worry, stress, boredom, anxiety, aggression, identity loss, remorse, and danger associated with improvement among prisoners who regularly engaged in some form of physical activity compared to those who did not. Second, prisoners who engaged in physical activity markedly improved their social skills and fitness levels. Third, it was revealed that prisoners who engaged in exercise or sport did so for enjoyment, fun, and a good feeling from the activity. He said that engagement in physical activity provides a good outlet for prisoners to think through some of these demands as a way of learning to adapt.

DISCUSSION

The significance of a multimodal rehabilitation strategy that acknowledges the many needs of PDLs and seeks to enable them to live healthier, more purposeful lives both inside and outside of prison. Establishing a welcoming atmosphere in prisons that puts PDLs' overall health first and encourages a smooth transition back into society. In order to guarantee fair access to treatment and assistance, it highlights the necessity of comprehensive policies that target a variety of facets of health and well-being in addition to tackling structural and social barriers. It draws attention to the difficulties and initiatives involved in meeting inmates' healthcare needs, especially those of people who are incarcerated (PDLs).

Ensuring the needs of vulnerable populations are addressed calls for a synchronized holistic approach in the health sector. One of the most ignored populations in health conversations is the First PDLs incarcerated within correctional facilities. Historically, the health of a PDL was associated with negligence, stigmatization, and systematic challenges from the jail environment setup. However, establishing the Comprehensive Wellness Rehabilitation Programs has always been a transformative initiative in advancing the well-being and health of the PDLs. The core of any comprehensive approach is engaging the PDLs with various wellness activities. The viewing of PDLs as intrinsic beings with the right to health facilitates their professional and emotional empowerment. Structured activities, such as exercise, therapy sessions, and creative outlets, offer personal growth and rehabilitation venues within Correctional facilities. Comprehensive Wellness Rehabilitation Programs' success is also based on healthcare that should be distributed through all personnel; not only does the PDL healthcare address concerns early and frequently, but health disparities are mitigated through the assessment and assistance of the habilitation professional. Whether chronic condition management or behavioral health support, Comprehensive Wellness Rehabilitation Programs ensures that no PDL is left behind in pursuing a healthy journey. Healthcare solutions are offered on an affordable, accessible basis. There are also calls for more funds to increase supporting facilities. PDLs no longer need to jump through bureaucratic hoops for essential medical assistance. Instead, they have access to various health services that meet the desired goals; they facilitate timely remedies to enhance overall health and wellness outcomes. Protocol management also contributes to making Comprehensive Wellness programs more well-woven. The latter incorporates the integration of clear criteria and steps necessary for efficient health provision to PDLs. Besides, it resolves the problem of past prisons' perceptions and difficulties and boosts responsibility in service responsiveness.

With the lack of nurses and other healthcare workers in the Philippines, health is crucial in this marginalized group. Health care is often—if not most of the time, overlooked upon persons deprived of liberty as people with a negative perspective of them have influenced it. As student nurses, we must advocate for wellness and create an impact in health care for them, as they also deserve the tender love and care that everybody needs. In this matter, student nurses often choose their field of specialty in areas in the hospital. The researchers consider working as nurses in correctional facilities as it also enhances their skills and broadens their perspective as nurses. Improving nursing skills such as vital signs monitoring, primary emergency care for injuries, pharmacology study, and prenatal care is also essential in caring for PDLs.

Overall, the impact of Comprehensive Wellness Rehabilitation Programs is not limited to correctional facilities. With the introduction of e-visits and online hearings, PDLs can now communicate with loved ones at a distance and eradicate the geographical barriers to access to judicial trials. Increases in sleep rotations, a change in environment, and involvement in purposeful activity all increase the well-being of PDLs, allowing for a greater sense of dignity and identity in extreme conditions.

Therefore, the researchers should stand at the forefront of driving health transformation regarding PDLs. Advocate for implementing and expanding the Comprehensive Wellness Rehabilitation Programs from within the individual capacities in the health disposition. It can play an active part in ensuring that PDLs are adequately taken care of and that their fundamental rights to health and humanity are honored. The Comprehensive Wellness Rehabilitation Programs program offers a ray of hope for PDLs in the penal and incarceration environment. These programs offer a holistic solution by meeting the wellness needs of the PDLs involved and actively encouraging them to participate in ensuring they have a bright and promising life.

Conclusions

Based on the indicated findings, the following conclusions were drawn to show the need to provide individuals deprived of liberty (PDLs) in correctional facilities with comprehensive healthcare. These themes include organizing programs to support mental and physical health and guaranteeing overall well-being and recovery. Furthermore, programs are in place to include PDLs in various health activities to dispel stigma and build resilience. Healthcare evaluation and assistance protocols are prioritized, emphasizing ensuring equity, removing care obstacles, and enforcing procedures. Accessible healthcare is also prioritized through updated facilities, effective referral protocols, and timely medical care. Finally, organized protocols that include routine evaluations and emergency reactions serve as a framework for administering health services in correctional facilities. At some point, these principles protect PDLs' dignity and well-being by promoting a kind and all-encompassing approach to healthcare.

The topics covered in correctional institutions for People Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) emphasize the significance of comprehensive healthcare and behavioral management. The physical, mental, emotional, and behavioral needs of PDLs are all addressed by these activities. For PDLs to be prepared for reintegration into society and to promote recovery, systematic programs—like consistent exercise routines, counseling sessions, treatments, and vocational training—must be implemented. Protocol management in facilities also guarantees respect for laws and regulations, which helps create a secure and encouraging atmosphere favorable to constructive development. This is made possible by the collaboration of officers and PDLs. Targeting behavioral modification through interrelated developmental features, the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) created the Therapeutic Community Modality Program (TCMP) as an example of this method. These programs strive to facilitate rehabilitation, lower recidivism rates, and uphold the dignity and well-being of PDLs in correctional environments by addressing behavioral management and offering chances for personal growth.

Recommendations

After having comprehensively understood the study and outlined the findings identified, the researchers recommend the following solutions be considered:

Future Researchers. The researchers suggest that staff should know the most prevalent hospital patients' conditions and PDLs. Similarly, the well-being of the PDLs should still be a serious consideration. The dignity of every person should be preserved, and treating the PDLs should meet the established ethical standards. The investigation should also be shared, and future topics should be considered. Similarly, the study should be available to a broader audience to prevent misconceptions about the individuals.

Government / BJMP. The researchers recommend increased resource allocation of healthcare staffing, training, and continuous medical education to enhance service quality. Develop some specialized programs like the Parenting and Family Support Program that offer a helping hand to parents, giving them tools and guidance to connect with their kids and become better caregivers. From parenting classes to counseling and supervised visits, strengthening the bond of the PDLs with their family. Self-Assessment and Personal Development Program, a journey of self-discovery and improvement. Through journals, mindfulness activities, workshops, and deep discussions, participants explore their values, strengths, and dreams, paving the way for personal growth and fulfillment.

Strengthen the relationship and partnerships with external health providers, NGOs, and Community-Based Organizations to increase access and improve gap-filling systems. Develop stigma policy programs that cannot segregate or discriminately alert PDLs access and create equitable access to healthcare.

Facilities. The researchers suggest that investment in medical facilities at correctional facilities will improve the healthcare system's infrastructure. In addition to expanding the capacity to handle a larger population of PDLs, improving the infrastructure will create a conducive environment for PDLs.

Public Awareness. The researchers recommend that people talk about their experiences of change during their incarceration, help young individuals avoid criminal acts that they may regret in the future, and help people understand better their different experiences inside the jail and how they cope with those experiences to be better people.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting the study, ethical considerations were prioritized in conducting the study to ensure the well-being and rights of the participating healthcare workers and officers or wardens. Researchers abide by all relevant laws, rules, and regulations. Before data collection, informed consent is acquired, and participant protection measures are incorporated into the research design.

Additionally, researchers work to optimize any potential rewards from their work. Participation in this research is optional, and individuals retain the freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without facing any negative consequences. The names and identities of study participants will not be disclosed, and all information will be maintained and managed with the highest confidentiality.

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